

House Price Prediction Using Linear Regression, Random Forest and Decision Tree Algorithms

Ameena sherin.v
PG Student
Dept. of computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam
Ameenasherinv2022a@mca.ajce.in

Ms. Ankitha philip.
Asst. Professor
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam
ankithaphilip@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Nowadays, housing prices rise every year, requiring the creation of a system that can predict future house values. People want to acquire a house with the help of their budgets and market research tactics. As a result, the primary purpose of our research is to precisely predict the price of a home while avoiding losses. There are several factors to consider when predicting home costs, and clients should attempt to estimate efficient home prices based on their budget and preferences.

As a result, we're developing a house price forecasting model. Linear Regression, Decision Tree algorithm, and Random Forest algorithm are examples of machine learning algorithms. The outcome of this study ensures that the house price is as accurate as possible.

Keywords:

Linear Regression, Random Forest, Decision Tree, Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

House is one of the most basic necessities of human life along with basic necessities like food, water and so on. Long ago, the price of a property was decided manually. But the problem is that, there is 25% error occurred and such effect is loss of money. But now there is a big change in old technology. machine learning algorithms are used to predict house price.

Machine learning relies heavily on data. Essentially, machine learning entails constructing these. Previous data samples will also be utilized to predict fresh data. The remaining 20% of data from the known dataset is utilized for testing and the remaining 80% is used for training. Because our population is growing at a rapid pace, market demand for housing is increasing. As a result, the demand for housing in cities is expanding. People who are unaware of a home's true value and lose money as a result of their ignorance. Different Machine Learning approaches are utilized to forecast the house price in this study, including Linear Regression, Decision Tree Regression, and Random Forest Regression. There are various advantages for home

purchasers, home investors, and home sellers. There are several benefits to home buyers or a home investors and home builders can gain the benefits of a house price prediction model. This model will provide a lot of information knowledge to house buyers, property investors and house builders, as well as current house valuation market, it will help them to find out the price of the house.

At the same time, this model can help potential buyers to determine the features of a house they want according to their budget. It focuses on forecasting home prices based on the machine learning model, as well as analysis of the attributes used primarily in the previous study affecting the price of the house.

With the use of real-time data from residences in Pune, India, the initiative tries to anticipate property prices using machine learning techniques. This statistical research is designed to help us better understand the link between home attributes and how these factors are utilized to forecast property value. To determine the price of a home, we use a variety of algorithms. The issue is that forecasted costs fluctuate depending on how accurate they are. We calculate the average of these projections to avoid this issue. As a result, it aids in the prevention of errors. The results showed that this method was less inaccurate and more precise than using individual methods. This project's purpose is to create a machine learning model that can reliably assess the worth of a house given a set of options. All of this suggests that house price prediction is a new field of study that necessitates machine learning expertise.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

We will look at various machine learning algorithms in order to enhance price prediction in this conference paper. Housing spending patterns reflect the current economic climate and are inextricably linked to buyers and sellers. A home's price is governed by a number of criteria, including the number of bedrooms, bathrooms, and the median age of the house. Real estate agencies used to estimate house prices by hand a few years ago. That prediction, however, is 25 percent off the mark. Both buyers and sellers lose money as a result.

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To predict property prices, Anurag Sinha [1] used a variety of machine learning approaches. This analysis employs Ordinary Least Squares techniques. The size of the space, the number of bedrooms, the number of bathrooms, the drawing room, the house, and, most significantly, the square footage for each area were all used to determine the price. As the scope of this paper for forecasting house prices, several metrics are used for feature extraction, these variables are called feature data sets. The study reveals that it greatly influenced the location of the home.

Anand G.Rawooli Et al [2] are proposed a " House Price Prediction using a Machine Learning Model": A Survey of Literature. This paper pointed the house price prediction using multiple linear regression and ANN. It focus on its attributes such as locational, structural, neighborhood. This Accurate prediction model helps the investors or house buyers to determine the realistic price of a house.

Dhinesh Kumar et al. [3] proposed [April 2021]: Prediction of Property Price and Possibility Using Machine Learning: This study discusses property prediction, as well as novel insight possibilities and machine learning methodologies. Using linear regression, Random Forest, and gradient boosting, we were able to forecast the price of a property. To summarize, the price of a property and a house is determined by the features that are required for the property. The model's final forecast will be utilized to provide fresh insights for future scenarios.

The "House Price Prediction Using Machine Learning and Neural Networks" is proposed by Abhijit Sarma et al [4]. The technology that seeks to deliver an accurate property price prediction. Linear Regression, Forest Regression, Boosted Regression, and Neural Networks are all used in the system. Customers will be satisfied with this technique since it produces precise results and eliminates the risk of making a bad house investment.

Sifei Lu [5] proposed a hybrid regression technique for predicting home prices. The creative feature engineering method is studied in this study using a small dataset and data characteristics. The proposed method was recently used in the Kaggle Challenge "House Price: Advanced Regression Techniques" as the main kernel. The goal of the article is to predict appropriate pricing for clients based on their financial situation and priorities.

III. MOTIVATION

The real estate industry is not as transparent as it used to be. It is difficult to predict future house values due to the continually changing nature of the market. This is why we decided to conduct a research project that aims to provide house price prediction technique. The results of this study are not only based on the techniques used in the pathway, but also on the average of various techniques to achieve the most accurate results.

Physical characteristics, location, and the number of bedrooms are all elements that influence house costs. Forecasting has typically relied on these elements. On the other hand, such prediction systems demand specific subject expertise and experience. Machine Learning techniques have expanded the number of ways to analyze, forecast, and visualize housing values.

IV. METHADODOLOGY

A. Data Source

The dataset used here for training the model is taken from Kaggle. Kaggle is a collection of datasets that are used for implementing machine learning algorithms. Housing.csv dataset is used for house prediction using different algorithms. Each row represents a district and there are 10 attributes in the dataset. That is Longitude, latitude, housing median age, total rooms, total bedrooms, population, households, median income, median house value, ocean proximity. There are 20,640 instances in the dataset. All attributes are numeric except for the ocean proximity field. The dataset is used for model training. The system provides user input in webpage. This user inputs are used to predict house price. Flask framework is used to connect these UI and python code.

B. Stratified Sampling on Dataset

The next step is to use stratified sampling to sample the dataset. But you can learn everything you need to know about why we need to do it right here. You're now prepared to do stratified sampling based on income level. ShuffleSplit and StratifiedKFold are combined in StratifiedShuffleSplit. The proportion of class labels in the train and test datasets is nearly equal when using StratifiedShuffleSplit.

C. Finding Correlations

You can use the corr() method to rapidly determine the standard correlation coefficient between each pair of characteristics because the dataset isn't too large. The correlation ranges between -1 and 1. When it is close to 1, it shows a positive correlation, and when it is close to -1, it suggests a negative correlation. When it's close to 0, it means the two variables don't have a linear relationship. Let's revisit the correlation matrix, this time include three additional columns: rooms per household, bedrooms per room, and people per home.

D. Data Preparation

This is the most important stage before training a machine learning model for the purpose of predicting housing prices. Let's go ahead and execute all of the required data transformations. There are a number of data transformation procedures that must be completed in the proper order. Fortunately, Scikit-Learn has the Pipeline class to assist you with such transformation sequences. A basic pipeline for numeric attributes is shown below. Pipeline is a tool that helps us keep our code clean and maintainable. TransformmerMixin is used to transform inputs in this step. BaseEstimator is a programme that is used to fit and convert data.

E. Linear Regression for House Price Prediction with Python

The methodology of regression analysis is used to determine the relationship between variables. The regression equation, often known as the correlation coefficient, can be used to

evaluate the relationship between the variables. To determine which attributes are most important in explaining the dependent variable, linear regression models can be utilized. Linear regression analysis provides for certain price estimates by recording independent and dependent variable data. The power of the linear regression model may be observed when the value of the relationship between dependent and independent variables is quantified. To describe improvements to an independent variable with a dependent variable, use linear regression modelling. Along with other factors such as house prices, house size, property type, number of bedrooms, and so on, the house price forecast can be used as an independent and dependent variable. As a result, the house price is designated as a dependent variable, while the other attributes are designated as independent variables, allowing the key variables to be found by calculating each attribute's correlation coefficient.

```
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
lin_reg = LinearRegression()
lin_reg.fit(housing_prepared, housing_labels)

data = housing.iloc[:1]
labels = housing_labels.iloc[:1]
data_preparation = full_pipeline.transform(data)

print("Linear Regression Predictions: ",
lin_reg.predict(data_preparation))
```

F. Decition Tree

A Decition tree algorithm is a machine learning technique for discovering patterns in data by learning decision rules. The three types of nodes in the Decision Tree algorithm are the Root Node, Interior Node, and Leaf Node. The internal nodes reflect the features of a data collection, while the branches represent the decision rules. That is the difference between housing labels and housing preparedness. The Decision Tree Regressor analyses attributes and trains a tree-based model to forecast future data and produce useful output. The Decision Tree The regressor learns the maximum and lowest depths of the graph and evaluates the data according to the system.

```
tr_regressor = DecisionTreeRegressor()
tr_regressor.fit(housing_prepared, housing_labels)
data = housing.iloc[:1]
labels = housing_labels.iloc[:1]
data_preparation = full_pipeline.transform(data)
print("Decision Tree Predictions:
tr_regressor.predict(data_preparation))
```

G. Random Forest

The sklearn Random Forest Regressor is used to predict house price. To fit our model, we'll use housing prepared and housing labels. We've put the model together and observed its performance. Let's try to guess the prices of the houses in the real-world data. It is feasible to forecast housing values fairly accurately. To forecast the price of a house, RandomForestRegressor() is utilized.

```
rf_regressor = RandomForestRegressor()
rf_regressor.fit(housing_prepared, housing_labels)
data = housing.iloc[:1]
labels = housing_labels.iloc[:1]
data_preparation = full_pipeline.transform(data)
print("Random Forest Predictions: ",
rf_regressor.predict(data_preparation))
```

H. Average of these three predictions

We use different algorithms to determine the price of a house. The problem is that predicted prices vary according to their accuracy. To avoid this problem, we calculate the average of these predictions. So, it helps to avoid people making mistakes.to find average we define Average() function.

```
def Average(my_list):

avg = sum(my_list) / len(my_list)

return avg

my_list = [lin_reg.predict(data_preparation),
tr_regressor.predict(data_preparation),
rf_regressor.predict(data_preparation)]

print("average", Average(my_list))
```

I. Result

Result is shown in this figure in figure 1.It is accurate price of the house.

Figure 1

V. CONCLUSION

The paper " House Price Prediction Using Linear Regression, Random Forest and Decision Tree Algorithms" explains how to estimate house prices using three different algorithms: Linear Regression, Decision Tree, and Random Forest, each based on different features of the data. The problem is that projected expenses fluctuate based on their accuracy. To avoid this problem, we calculate the average of these projections. As a result, it helps to prevent mistakes. This average price represents a reasonable assessment of a home's worth. Customers will be satisfied with the procedure because it will produce precise results and reduce the chance

of purchasing in the incorrect location. As a major future upgrade, more features to estimate the price could be added.

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